

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Vocational School English Analysis (IKN-Sains)

Object;

Rebecca Paper Analysis for *EDUCATIONAL VALUES IN THE FILM OF SING 2016*

Background and Analysis

Abstract

At the end of 2016 Illumination Entertainment released an animated film entitled 'Sing'. Sing's animated film has been loved by many people in the world, especially children. This film managed to reap revenues of around Rp. 1 trillion in 5 days. This film tells the story of Buster Moon's efforts to maintain the theater building that his late father had bought. Moon came up with an idea to increase the number of theatergoers by opening a singing competition. The study in this paper aims to examine and analyze the educational value of the Sing film. In this study, researchers conducted an assessment using a qualitative method which will show the educational value in the 2016 film Sing.

Conclusion

The educational values contained in the 2016 film Sing are quite a lot, such as always being optimistic in living life, not easily giving up on circumstances, rising from adversity, having creative ideas, and supporting each other between friends. Sing's animated film is very inspiring and this film also managed to get many positive reviews from the audience. The essence of this film is very simple, which is to teach us to always want to try, again and again (Treasure & Crane, 2016). Ups and downs are common. But achieving a dream is a wonderful thing.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

= Yes, available. The data is obtained from articles that have been made.

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

= This data was obtained through direct documentation from the 2016 film Sing and several other articles to support the data.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

= The research that I made is the result of the initial research that no one else has made. However, in general, analyzing the value of education has been done in many other films.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

= This research provides education in the progress of the times that lack knowledge of educational values. Of course, this research will also provide new knowledge and add insight to those who read.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

= This research is generally about issues in everyday life. Like giving up easily, not having friends, lack of confidence, and others.

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

= The problem taken in this article is about educational values. This problem has been answered and has been widely developed in the community. for example, providing education on educational values in cartoons.

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

= The problem raised is regarding the educational values that need to be applied. These educational values are very common to know and apply to every individual.

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

= The events that occur in this study are about the ups and downs of the heyday of one of the characters. He experienced conflicts in his life, then he regained his former glory.

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9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

= The results of this study are very useful for the community. This study explains the importance of applying educational values in everyday life. For example, this article explains the importance of mingling with others, sharing love with others, helping each other, always having creative ideas in doing things, and not giving up easily in any situation.

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